

Feasibility Report on Deployability and Use of 5 Safes Test Execution Service in Three Production Environments

PANORAMA Work Package 2 Final Report

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Executive Summary

This work package evaluated whether the [Five Safes Task Execution Service \(5STES\)](#) can be installed and operated in multiple trusted research environments within the NHS SDE Network (Yorkshire & Humber, North East North Cumbria and North West NHS Secure Data Environments), and what conditions would be required in its current development state to make this feasible to support federated analytics.

A pilot examination of the production-readiness of 5STES was conducted in the individual environments from September 2025 – November 2025. The individual assessment reports are included as appendices (AWS- and Azure-based), and this report provides a generalised applicability across diverse environments (AWS-based, Azure-based, hybrid, on-premises, high-maturity, and low-maturity TREs).

At the time of the feasibility assessment, 5STES was not currently suitable for install and usability in the three environments as a production system for handling sensitive data, due to three main challenges:

(1) Local environment constraints; (2) Prototype / R&D-stage immaturity; and (3) Fundamental design and network-wide limitations. The system complexity at the time of evaluation is the primary barrier to adoption. However, its architectural direction is promising and could become

viable TREs/SDEs in future if complexity is reduced, common deployment patterns are provided, and federation behaviours are clarified and standardised. Ongoing development to reduce the complexity, clear documentation and supporting development (e.g., GUIs) and software governance mechanisms would also support its wider adoption and use within a federated data ecosystem.

1. Background: Federated Analytics

1.1. The challenge of federated research

The acceleration of sensitive data research is often contingent upon accessing large, diverse and distributed datasets. Sensitive data for research must undergo rigorous public benefit evaluation and requires pseudonymisation and minimisation to protect public confidentiality and privacy that comply with stringent governance and technical controls (known as the 'Five Safes Principles'). Even with these measures, data controllers have concerns that traditional centralised data warehousing methods (e.g., data pooling in a single location from multiple data providers) are often unfeasible due to legal, ethical, and organisational constraints. Methods have been developed to enable analysis across multiple trusted environments (a 'federation') without compromising security or moving the underlying raw data, known as federated analytics [1, 2, 3].

1.2. 5 Safes Test Execution Service (5STES)

Five Safes Test Execution Service (5STES) is presented as a novel technical solution being developed by the DARE UK TREvolution Programme. 5STES —a "Weave"— designed to facilitate the secure, remote execution of standardised analyses within this distributed, siloed ecosystem. Built upon the GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES) and conforming to international open standards from GA4GH and ELIXIR, 5STES is being engineered specifically to meet the high governance and technical standards for privacy and confidentiality of sensitive data inherent to TREs.

5STES is designed to support a federated analytics model. In this model, the foundational principle is that data remains in place within its secure TRE and is mapped to a common data model. Researchers write their analysis code using the common data model vocabulary, and the 'lead' TRE sends pre-approved analysis code to other partners within the federation for execution. The resulting analysed, aggregate data is then returned to the 'lead' TRE. This system separates responsibilities:

- *TRE Managers* register their environments, manage projects, and authorise researcher access.
- *Researchers* submit GA4GH TES analyses (the analytical code) for execution.
- *Remote Agents* at participating TREs automatically collect and run these approved analyses, even supporting offline environments by pre-loading container images.

5STES also aims to integrate strict disclosure control, the process of checking the researchers' analyses that they intend to publish before releasing them from the TRE. In 5STES, results generated by the remote agents pass through a controlled egress process. This mandatory review step ensures that outputs are scrutinised by TRE governance staff to prevent any disclosive data from being released. The design of 5STES is to separate the federated analysis

into logical stages to ensure technical and governance constraints of sensitive data research are met.

1.3. PANORAMA feasibility of 5STES

PANORAMA is an Early Adopter in the DARE UK TREvolution Programme. PANORAMA partners are Yorkshire & Humber NHS Secure Data Environment, North East North Cumbria NHS Secure Data Environment, and North West NHS Secure Data Environment, facilitated by researchers at the University of Sheffield. PANORAMA aimed to test the feasibility of the deployability and usability of 5STES in the three live environments. From September – November 2025, the partners conducted a pilot consisting of an evaluation of 5STES in the current development state. One of the environments is on AWS-cloud, and two environments are on Azure Cloud. We have included specific findings in the appendices. For this report, we have generalised findings to support the 5STES development team for a range of TRE infrastructures and maturity (e.g. low maturity TREs vs high maturity TREs).

We have structured this report in plain language for a wider non-technical audience. We provide a clear explanation of the technology, to document the findings regarding deployability of 5STES within individual partners and across the federation during the feasibility period. Whilst we have captured challenges, our report's goal is to distinguish between issues specific to the PANORAMA federation and more generalisable findings, articulating what is inherently fixable (but must change) in 5STES itself to improve deployability into any live environment to support federated analytics. It is important to note that since 5STES is in active development, the development team may have already addressed some or all of these observations and recommendations at the time of writing (Nov/Dec 2025).

Finally, we have also articulated a risk matrix for any 'in development' product (e.g., non-production ready) to assess risks for deploying and using in a live, real-world environment.

2. Methodology

The feasibility methodology integrated a thorough review of the existing 5STES documentation at the time of feasibility, technical installation attempts and an architectural analysis. It involved comparisons with similar technology, in order to contextualise it against a similar tool that supports aspects of federated analytics. Finally, the review consisted of consultation with software engineering, platform and SDE operations experts, who also considered aspects of information security and data governance. Each PANORAMA partner has provided a summary report of the feasibility of 5STES within Appendix 2; the partner names have been de-identified for cybersecurity reasons. It is important to note that we were unable to execute an end-to-end federated workflow across the PANORAMA partners. Two of the three partners were not able to install and test 5STES in the time period due to its development stage. The third partner was able to deploy in a test environment only, but the 5STES version available at the time did not meet the minimum criteria for installing in a production environment.

3. 5STES Architecture

3.1. High-level architecture and requirements

The 5STES is heavily micro-architecture driven, being built of many individual docker containers. An indicative list can be found [here](#). These are organised into three distinct parts;

- Submission layer which holds requests and returned data.
- TRE Layer which polls the Submission layer, initiates tasks and handles Egress.
- Data Layer which comprises Funnel, Trino and the data source.

[Funnel](#) is an implementation of the [GA4GH Task Execution Schemas](#). This is a server program which receives a JSON request which contains a destination for the data, a container to run the analysis in and the commands to run in that container. See Figure 3 (below) executors for an example of running ‘echo “Hello World”’ in an Ubuntu docker container (note: a [guide](#) is now available with the ‘Hello World’ executors).

[Trino](#) is a Java project that provides access to multiple different data sources, enabling the querying of multiple databases or CSV files through a consistent interface.

The data itself must be arranged in an Observational Medical Partnerships ([OMOP](#)) Common Data Model (CDM).

The Egress Bucket is marked in red to indicate that it is a manual step requiring approval by an authorised TRE user. Approval by one TRE has no bearing whatsoever on any other TRE.

Authentication to either of the layers is handled by Keycloak, but this can be handed off to other SSO providers and would require either adding another SSO provider or managing credentials for an individual.

Each organisation within the federation must implement the full architecture stack and implement network connections between each TRE layer and any submission layers.

3.2. 5STES internal networking

As 5STES is built around a microarchitecture approach, there are connections required between each component. The next two diagrams show networking for the submission and TRE layers respectively; these are generated from the docker-compose files in the [DARE-TRE-FX-Environment repository](#) (an early iteration of 5STES in the DARE UK Phase 1 programme).

Figure 1: Submission layer

Figure 2: TRE Layer

The submission layer contains the following containers:

- Nginx-dare - provides a proxy layer
- SubmissionUI - provides a front-end to the submission layer
- SubmissionAPI - provides a REST API for the system

- Minio - provides an S3-style bucket for researchers to retrieve their data
- Postgresql - provides a database for persistent storage
- Rabbitmq - provides a log of jobs.
- Seq - provides a central logging source
- KeyCloak - provides for authentication and authorisation
- [Adminer](#) - A PHPMyAdmin type application (although purpose was not clear to the systems engineers reviewing 5STES)

The TRE layer utilises similar containers, with the SubmissionUI and SubmissionAPI being replaced with tre-ui, tre-api, DataEgress-ui and DataEgress-api.

3.3. Executing a researcher's analysis submission

Before a job can be started, the system requires some configuration. Within the submission layer a manager must create:

- a project;
- a TRE; and
- a user

The TRE and the user can then be added to the project. Next, this project must be approved in the TRE Layer by logging into the TRE UI and then, first, approving the project and, second, adding the user to the project's membership list. This enables a researcher to be able to log in as the user and submit tasks.

For a researcher to submit a job, they need to log into the submission system and find the Project's output bucket name and get an authorization token. Using these, you can POST a JSON request to the Submission API at <submission url>:5034/v1/tasks.

```
POST localhost:5034/v1/tasks
{
  "state": 0,
  "name": "Hello World",
  "inputs": [],
  "outputs": [
    {
      "name": "Stdout",
      "description": "Stdout results",
      "url": "s3://<outputBucketName>", // Set the output bucket
      "path": "/outputs",
      "type": "DIRECTORY"
    }
  ],
  "executors": [
    {
      "image": "ubuntu",
      "command": [
        "echo",
        "Hello World"
      ],
      "workdir": "/outputs",
      "stdout": "/outputs/stdout",
    }
  ],
  "volumes": null,
  "tags": {
```

```

    "project": "<ProjectName>", // Project that you would like to
submit to.
    "tres": "<TREName>" // TRE related to that Project
  },
  "logs": null,
  "creation_time": null
}

```

Figure 3: Example JSON supplied to Funnel

Once a user with egress privileges authorises the transfer of the data back to the submission layer, the researcher can then download the data from the submission bucket. It is important to note that for multiple TREs there appears to be no automatic amalgamation of the data.

3.4. Comparison with similar tooling

[Bunny](#) is the open-source federated analytics solution to simpler problems such as finding out how many patients meet a study's criteria and how these patients are distributed across criteria like age. It is again designed to work with OMOP Common Data Model. Bunny enables organisations to integrate with the HDRUK Gateway Cohort Discovery Tool.

To turn Bunny into a service requires another service that each Bunny can query for jobs, such as Relay or RQUEST. Relay uses rounding and suppression to avoid any indirect release of information.

Bunny can talk to both Postgresql and SQL Server databases (with the assumption SQL Alchemy is running things in the background, adding the possibility of supporting more data sources). However, for the docker image provided, the container still uses environment variables to provide access to the database. Like 5STES, querying the database uses JSON, but the format is somewhat different than that in Figure 4. For example:

```

{
  "task_id": "job-2023-01-13-14: 20: 38-project",
  "project": "project_id",
  "owner": "user1",
  "cohort": {
    "groups": [
      {
        "rules": [
          {
            "varname": "OMOP",
            "varcat": "Person",
            "type": "TEXT",
            "oper": "=",
            "value": "8507"
          }
        ]
      },
      {
        "rules_oper": "AND"
      }
    ],
    "groups_oper": "OR"
  },
  "collection": "collection_id",
  "protocol_version": "v2",
  "char_salt": "salt",
  "uuid": "unique_id"
}

```

Which results in;

```
{'uuid': 'unique_id', 'status': 'ok', 'collection_id': 'collection_id',  
'message': '', 'protocolVersion': 'v2', 'queryResult': {'count': 40,  
'datasetCount': 0, 'files': []}}
```

Figure 4: Cohort query and return using Bunny

Showing that 40 participants were returned in the example.

The docker container in the example shows the SQL used, showing the rounding and suppression of small results. 8507 is the `gender_concept` male and its definition is found in the `concepts` table. However, it was unclear to the engineer how Bunny decided that 8507 should be checked against the `gender_concept_id` field:

```
(SELECT person.person_id AS person_id  
FROM person  
WHERE person.gender_concept_id = 8507)  
SELECT round(count(*) / CAST(10 AS NUMERIC), 0) * 10 AS anon_1  
FROM (SELECT final_group_0.person_id AS person_id  
FROM final_group_0) AS anon_2  
HAVING count(*) >= 10
```

Figure 5: Example of rounding and suppression in Bunny

Bunny shows greater code maturity (i.e., is closer to a 'plug and play' state), and is actively maintained by the developers via versioning releases and bug fixes. Specifically, it has a number of key features that organisations may require for installation in a live environment, including:

- Contains a test suite;
- Policy of private vulnerability disclosure giving them time to address issues before going public;
- Uses feature branches;
- Has several contributors; and
- Testing and builds are managed automatically via GitHub Actions on merge.

In addition, Bunny is fundamentally less at risk of unauthorised data release, which is an advantage of its reduced scope.

4. Feasibility outcomes

For each architecture component, we summarise implementation requirements, network-wide implications and recommendations for the developers generalisable beyond the PANORAMA partners. These are derived from both the desk exercise, test installation and feedback from technical experts across the partners. The critical requirements for a federated implementation of 5STES is organised into the following categories: microservice/container architecture; authentication and identity federation; data storage and OMOP CDM implementation; and egress.

4.1. Microservice / container architecture

As noted previously, 5STES relies heavily on microarchitecture and containers. Although each container may function flawlessly, as the number of containers increase in the tool's build, so too does the complexity of the relationship between the containers and the likelihood of failure over the longer chain. This complexity is then amplified when 5STES is introduced within a federation. The initial estimates of the minimum operating requirements are: (1) 15-25 containers per TRE, interacting securely; (2) secure secrets storage; and (3) monitoring, upgrades, patching and governance logs.

Table 1: Feasibility

TRE Platform Expertise	Feasibility	Observations
High-expertise	Medium	For a team with a high-degree of development expertise, and with dedicated resourcing to support infrastructure and architecture development, implementation is possible at the current development stage of 5STES. However, the deployment and ongoing maintenance is still a 'high burden', which would be amplified further within a federation.
Medium-expertise	Low	In addition to the high-burden for deployment and ongoing maintenance, the current development stage of 5STES means that it would be difficult for a team to deploy and operate with a medium-level of expertise. This assumes that the level of expertise still has a high-degree of familiarity with containers.
Low-expertise or TRE outsourced to a third-party provider	Low	Infrastructure complexity is such that it would be unlikely that 5STES could be deployed or maintained in its current development state. For platforms outsourced to third-party providers, it would depend on the expertise and could be costly at this stage of development.

4.1.1. Requirements for federation

As discussed, complexity is multiplicative across microservices, and whilst a microservice architecture is technically elegant in supporting the Five Safes principles, it is operationally prohibitive for most SDEs. The wider TRevolution programme is working to develop a Kubernetes-based TRE (K8TRE), this may make 5STES easier to deploy for medium- and low-experienced teams. However, this does not remove complexity. It only moves complexity from one aspect of service to another, from the deployment and maintenance of 5STES in current architectures and infrastructures, to the complexity of deploying and maintaining a Kubernetes-based environment. However, in the longer-term with the widening adoption of Kubernetes, it may be the case that this complexity is common to a group of activities, so that efficiencies of scale may be possible.

4.1.2. Recommendations for developers

PANORAMA recommends producing a 'Bunny-style' 5STES variant (or version 1.0) with fewer services, especially for federated analytics. This would enable organisations with medium- and low-expertise to still be able to support federated analytics, but a 'simplified' version. Once

organisations and federations are able to support this initial state with confidence, development can progress to higher degrees of analytical complexity. An alternative would be to provide a fully-managed deployment (turn-key) option for TREs without DevOps teams, or fully-managed deployment across federations to ensure the functioning of multi-organisational integrated microservices. Finally, the feasibility assessment suggested the use of cloud-native equivalents (AWS MQ, RDS, Azure equivalents) to reduce container footprint. This particular suggestion was to improve the ‘plug-and-play’ readiness of the tool for use within a federated ecosystem.

4.2. Authentication and identity federations

The federation must agree and adopt a Federated Authentication system, such as the [OpenID Connect](#) (OIDC) identity authentication protocol, that standardises how users can sign in to applications and services securely (an older version of this is SAML). The protocol allows a user's identity to be verified by an ‘authorisation server’ and provides an ‘ID token’ (a type of [JSON Web Token](#)) to the application, enabling features like single sign-on (SSO) and preventing the need for separate passwords for every service.

Table 2: Feasibility across SDE Types

TRE Type	Feasibility	Typical Challenges
Azure-centric TRE	Low	Organisations often forbid running additional IDPs; Keycloak introduces duplication. Although Keycloak can offload onto other IDPs, it still adds duplication around assurance, monitoring and security (e.g. everything other than the username/password entry would have to be included as part of a user management audit).
AWS-centric TRE	High	Keycloak-compatible AWS services exist; but still increases operational burden.
Cloud-agnostic TRE	Medium	IDP choice is flexible but requires expertise to maintain.
On-prem TRE	High	May lack modern identity platforms with native OIDC support, requiring installation and long-term maintenance of an IDP. Higher operational burden on local IT teams to manage certificates, trust anchors, patching, and federation agreements. Network segmentation and restrictive firewall policies make multi-partner connectivity harder to implement and audit. May require additional investment to meet uptime, monitoring, and security requirements expected in federated architectures.

4.2.1. Requirements for federation

There must be a multi-partner trust model established and approved by the organisations’ security and networking experts, as well as the appropriate Information Governance (IG) in place between organisations to enable the connectivity. These aspects, however, cannot be over-stated in terms of the technical and non-technical aspects required. Technically, the network teams supporting the TRE must have

sufficient expertise and resourcing in creating and maintaining the authentication protocol. The IG must cover formal agreements and Standard Operating Procedures between the federation partners that define:

- The type and level of identity proofing, ongoing review of accounts to ensure they are correctly created, updated, suspended and removed and preventing 'orphaned identities' that retain access due to process misalignment.
- Local organisational policies (e.g. password lifecycle, MFA enforcement), and requires harmonisation across partners that may operate at different assurance levels.
- Cross-organisation auditability ensuring consistent logging, retention periods for logs, availability for cross-site incident investigations.
- Defining equivalence in assurance level across organisations with respect to MFA standards to a common standard to prevent a security compromise.
- Documented incident response coordination for incident reporting and notification, agreed procedures for revoking trust, pausing connectivity and reinstating services.
- Long-term maintenance responsibilities (i.e., patching, monitoring) must be assigned and formally assured, with processes for maintaining these within the federation clearly defined and documented.
- Authentication processes meet regulatory obligations (e.g., the identity controls satisfy the governing legislation between partners and any additional regulatory frameworks required).
- Appropriate Data Sharing Agreements and Data Processing Impact Assessments must cover all of the above, including liability definitions.

Within PANORAMA, which is likely to be generalisable to all existing and future federations, there is no standard identity approach, which means that establishing and maintaining authentication and identity management in a heterogeneous landscape will require establishing equivalence and bespoke tailored protocols as federations grow and evolve. Keycloak, the open source identity and access management solution inbuilt into the 5STES architecture, whilst robust, nevertheless introduces additional infrastructure maintenance overheads that organisations need to manage and maintain. Finally, many TREs lack staff or expertise to operate additional infrastructure, especially within the context of authentication and identity federation and supporting federated analytics.

4.2.2. Recommendations for developers

First we recommend some native support for AzureAD/Entra, AWS Cognito, GCP Identity. Recommendations include defining the high-level approach and design pattern to follow (provider-agnostic); articulating concrete integration points and standards to implement;

providing, where possible, provider-specific notes (e.g., AzureAD/Entra, AWS Cognito, GCP); and documenting a testing checklist for organisations to follow.

Second, we recommend publishing a ‘minimum identity pattern’ for all TREs to adopt. For developers of 5STES, we would recommend a concrete, practical pattern that TRE operates can adopt as a minimum baseline for identity and authentication. Although the aim is to create an interoperable, federated solution agnostic of existing architecture and infrastructure, we suggest a degree of prescriptiveness so organisations can converge on a small set of behaviours that can be audited and potentially automated.

4.3. Data storage and OMOP CDM implementation

Federated analytics relies on data that conforms to a Common Data Model (CDM) – for health data, this is specifically the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) CDM. The 5STES tool uses Trino, which requires metadata connectors (Hive/Iceberg) for non-relational stores. In order to support federated analytics using 5STES, each TRE must maintain OMOP synchronously otherwise the analysis cannot be supported. There is an assumption, then, that there is homogeneity between data availability, OMOP applied to the data, and consistency of OMOP within databases (or datasets), i.e., that the same variables have been mapped, which requires a coordinated ‘minimum’. This minimum will necessarily need to expand to expand the complexity of analysis that can be supported within federated analytics.

Table 3: OMOP CDM feasibility

TRE Type	Feasibility	Challenges
TREs already using relational OMOP	Medium	Straightforward but requires expert mapping, as well as a ‘minimum’ agreed OMOP set that will increase as the complexity of analysis increases.
TREs using Parquet, DuckDB or local formats	Medium	Requires major transformation or additional Trino configuration.
TREs with non-OMOPed data or legacy data stores	Very Low	Would need programme of OMOP mapping independent of 5STES deployment

4.3.1. Requirements for federation

For organisations that have previously mapped data into OMOP CDM using non-Trino configuration, this will require additional connectors to Trino to support federated analytics using 5STES. Whilst the degree to which will depend on the organisation, it may require substantial support to achieve compatibility with 5STES.

The requirements for federated analytics are far broader than just the 5STES tool. there is no agreed additional ‘minimum’ mapping to support federated analytics, and this will vary depending on the types of analysis. PANORAMA partners are in the process of mapping data to a network OMOP standard agreed in the NHS Secure Data Environment Network to support cohort discovery, which consists of 42 variables that can identify a relevant cohort of individuals. However, to support full-scale federated analysis, we have observed that organisations would likely need to convert data into OMOP, but many of these databases

contain thousands, or many thousands, of variables. To support limited federated analysis, there would need to be a minimum, but robust, set of standards agreed – which may still reach into the thousands of variables. This is a considerable overhead for organisations and the resourcing and funding required for this cannot be overstated. A data mapping exercise must also be completed within the federation, e.g., comparing databases or datasets available to ensure federation-wide coverage of the data, agreed mapping required, and the extent of mapping against the required mapping, etc., to assess the degree to which federated analytics can be supported operationally, outside of just the technical tools.

A final critical observation is that the PANORAMA partners only cover NHS England health and social care data and therefore largely conform to the OMOP CDM requirements (although social care is dependent on OMOP extensions to enable its conversion to OMOP CDM). For domains outside of health, this presents a challenge as domain-specific CDMs would be more appropriate for economic, administrative, environmental and many other types of sensitive data and may not align with the OMOP CDM. The degree to which these CDMs can be linked is a next-level challenge. Our feasibility indicates that 5STES can only currently support health research, and our observations are that its utility is currently only usable for health-specific federated analytics.

4.3.2. Recommendations for CDMs

The recommendations provided here are general recommendations, as they are beyond the scope of 5STES. The easiest of these recommendations is to provide examples of federated OMOP queries across organisations – that could then be used as the basis for testing materials for 5STES. For medium- and low-maturity TREs, these would be useful real-world examples of the aims of federated analytics. Second, a TRE-wide exercise to define minimum OMOP CDM compliance requirements across a spectrum (e.g., low, medium, high) would provide a clear roadmap towards operational success. Finally, insofar as possible, federations could develop standardised OMOP transformation pipelines, which would reduce the burden on organisations given the high degree of resourcing that OMOP requires. We recognise that these pipelines would need to be amended for each organisation, but providing templated pipelines may improve the speed of OMOPing against an organisation doing this from scratch. Similarly, this would improve consistency of mappings across organisations, potentially reducing data fidelity issues.

4.4. Egress

5STES incorporates manual approval by specially trained staff at each TRE, which is consistent with the approach taken in earlier research around semi-automation, and which was overwhelmingly favoured by members of the public when considering their requirements in sensitive data research [4, 5]. The Egress Bucket is marked in red to indicate that it is a manual step requiring approval by an authorised TRE user, which supports the ‘Safe Outputs’ aspect of the Five Safes Framework. The egress mechanism covers the analysed data being sent back to the ‘prime’ TRE.

4.4.1. Feasibility

The feasibility assessment showed that 5STES has a functioning egress mechanism that reflects the working of TREs, however the challenge will be around the SOPs of egress in the context of federated analytics.

As egress is a manual step in 5STES, there is the inevitability of egress accumulation, audit and versioning, particularly in the context of federated analytics. This may cause delays in results of analysis being sent back to researchers or risks around sharing out-of-date or potentially disclosive analyses without that will require strict Service Level Agreements (SLAs) between.

The processes supporting federated output statistical disclosure control will be crucial to managing workload and egress accumulation in the context of federated analytics. In Work Package 3, PANORAMA (in collaboration with other Early Adopter projects VISTA and SOCRATES), we have established a Federated Output Checking Principles document which can support federations in establishing good practice. In addition to principles, detailed standard operating procedures must be agreed in line with any project-specific requirements, suppression thresholds and other requirements set by the data controllers and project ethics.

4.4.2. Egress recommendations

As with data storage and common data models, the recommendations here are broader than 5STES. Although the tool supports egress, it raises a number of operational challenges since egress is a critical step in assuring no sensitive data is shared to researchers.

Integration with the SACRO tool offers some benefits to create and share provenance, audit and versioning records between federated partners. This would help to control some risks (although not all) around egress accumulation. This might also offer a semi-automated mechanism to support suppression of small numbers and improve the speed of egress in federated analytics.

Two final solutions in the context of federated analytics could be to create a central clearinghouse model within the federation for output review. All egress of any of the partners would be done centrally, improving consistency and accuracy and minimising inconsistent decision-making. However, this would require significant overhead to operationalise, and, like the adoption of Kubernetes to support 5STES, shifts complexity from one area to another. Similarly, a formal, agreed (inter)national standard for suppression would decrease inconsistent decision-making, but would require (inter)national agreement from all data controllers on those standards.

5. Risk assessment

It is important to note that we were unable to execute an end-to-end federated workflow across the PANORAMA partners. As articulated previously, this was due to the development stage of 5STES during our feasibility assessment period (September – November 2025). Two of the three partners were not able to install and test 5STES in the time period due to its development stage. The third partner was able to deploy in a test environment only, but the 5STES version available at the time did not meet the minimum criteria for installing in a production environment.

The risks highlighted have been categorised into Local (Specific) Risks, which are not necessarily generalisable, and Generalisable Risks which would be relevant to a number of organisations. The Generalisable Risks are applicable to 5STES (Software Maturity Risks) as well as broad risks with supporting federated analytics. It is important to highlight that 5STES is in active development, so the risks identified were correct at the time of feasibility, and may

have already been partially or fully addressed by the 5STES development team at the time of writing this report (November – December 2025).

5.1. Local / specific risks

For the partner that was able to deploy and execute a ‘Hello World’ test in its test environment, there were several key risks and issues found. They centre on the incompatibility of 5STES with the architecture of the local environment, which would either require customisation of the tool, or customisation of the environment to support its everyday use. In either case, this presented a significant risk around support outlay – both for initial usability as well as long-term support.

A detailed report can be found in Appendix 1, but the local risks were as follows:

- Port reporting. No active ability to report on which ports are required between which services to support configuration between the TRE and Submission layer and between the Egress bucket and the Submission bucket.
- Secrets security. Whilst SSO may provide some extra security, it would also require extra connection to the TRE layer. Additional measures may need to be taken to encrypt the transfer between the TRE Layer and the Funnel/Trino layer, depending on the configuration. The workaround would be to use a Secrets Manager in some places, but this would deviate from the standard 5STES architecture.
- Containers not being compatible with vulnerability checking software (CrowdStrike). Mitigations are to use sidecars or native solutions, but either solution would be deviating from the standard 5STES stack.
- Existing OMOP databases in Parquet. 5STES assumes that the OMOP database is stored in a relational database, whereas the local databases are in Parquet. Although Trino mitigates to some extent, it requires the use of a metadata connector (e.g., Hive/Iceberg) which may affect functionality.
- Container vulnerability goes unreported. Standard scanning in the environment is on a fortnightly basis, which may not be sufficient, especially in 5STES current development state.

It should be noted that the above environment-specific risks could also be applicable to other environments, so these have been adopted into generalised ‘technical risks’.

5.2. Generalised risks

Generalised risks are presented in the below tables and would need to be assessed by individual organisations and subsequently, the federation as a whole.

Table 4: Risk Assessment: Technical, Architecture, and Infrastructure Risks

ID	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Responsibility	Mitigation
T1	Inter-TRE network connectivity is difficult to configure or cannot meet security requirements.			Network / Platforms teams	Define minimal ports; use standard encrypted channels; pre-agreed inter-org trust models.
T2	Identity federation integration (OIDC / SSO) is complex or incompatible with local IdP.			Platforms / Identity teams	Support multiple IDPs; provide adapter patterns; central guidance; SCIM for lifecycle.
T3	Container runtime or orchestration platform incompatibilities (ECS/K8s/on-prem)			Platforms	Use reference images; publish supported base layers; test matrix.
T4	Inadequate handling of secrets or credentials within TRE execution layers.			Platforms / Security	Use cloud-native secret stores; enforce key rotation; minimal secret exposure.
T5	Cross-organisation data access patterns create performance or compatibility issues (e.g., Parquet vs relational OMOP).			Platforms / Data Engineering	Use abstraction layers; support multiple connectors (Trino etc); metadata catalogues.
T6	Limited support for running user-specified containers / workflows within restricted TRE environments.			TRE Operator	Provide approved base images; private registries; sandboxing.
T7	Lack of high availability / unclear failure behaviours across distributed services.			Platforms / Central Service	Define HA patterns; retry logic; message queue durability; maintenance windows.

Table 5: Risk Assessment: Governance & Data Protection Risks

ID	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Responsibility	Mitigation
G1	Inconsistent identity assurance or user vetting across TREs.			Org IG team	Minimum identity pattern; MFA; shared policies
G2	Risk of authorised or unauthorised disclosure of PII through federated outputs.				Standardised egress policy; community of practice; audit trails
G3	Cross-organisation incident response coordination unclear.			IG / Security / Central	Joint IR playbook; shared contacts; contractual terms.
G4	Researcher collusion or misuse of outputs.			All partners	Contractual control; audit logs; query history; egress constraints.
G5	Cross-border / cross-jurisdiction data governance issues			Legal / IG	Clear data-sharing agreements; SCCs (if required).

Table 6: Risk Assessment: Operational Delivery & Resourcing Risks

ID	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Responsibility	Mitigation
O1	Operational burden for provisioning and maintaining software and associated supporting services is high.			All teams	Cost models; support estimates; agreements between partners.
O2	Delays in authorisation or egress reduce system usability.				SLA definitions; workflow automation; triage queues.
O3	Insufficient training for TRE operators and researchers.			Training / TRE Ops	Standard induction training; shared materials.
O4	Lack of central catalogue of datasets / TRE capabilities.			All partners	Federated registry; governance for updates
O5	Researchers cannot easily clarify data anomalies with individual TRES.			Data Owners	Define data inquiry channels; metadata availability.

Table 7: Risk Assessment: Ecosystem and Strategic Risks

ID	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Responsibility	Mitigation
E1	Competing platforms reach critical mass and reduce adoption.			Unclear	Interoperability; open standards; demonstrable value.
E2	Insufficient researcher uptake undermines cost-effectiveness.			Unclear	Engagement strategy; usability improvements.
E3	Data owners restrict federation due to trust or IG objections.			IG/Governance	Strong IG model; transparency; proven controls.

Table 8: Risk Assessment: Software Maturity and Development Process Risks

ID	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Responsibility	Mitigation
S1	Software is research-grade (e.g., non-production ready) with rapidly evolving architecture.			Vendor / Central Development	Clear versioning; roadmap visibility; LTS releases.
S2	Lack of stable branches or release processes leads to risk when applying fixes.			Vendor	Introduce stable branch + patch-only model; CI/CD gating.
S3	Missing or incomplete automated testing (unit, integration, E2E).			Vendor	Add test coverage, regression suites, security testing.
S4	Vulnerabilities in containers or dependencies may not be disclosed or patched quickly.			Vendor / Security	SLA for CVE disclosure; automated scanning; patch cycle.
S5	Limited documentation on system architecture, federation flows, or deployment.			Vendor	Comprehensive documentation; diagrams; deployment cookbooks
S6	Limited documentation on production readiness.			Vendor	Comprehensive technology governance, including security and compliance; change management; and documentation/auditability

6. Discussion and recommendations for future development

Despite feasibility barriers during the assessment period (September – November 2025), there are a number of promising opportunities for the developers of 5STES to focus on to improve the tool to a ‘production ready’ state in the coming months.

The PANORAMA partners felt that on the whole, the conceptual architecture is technically sound, with robust components including Trino and Funnel, and the overall design aligns with best practice to support sensitive data federated analytics, adhering to the Five Safes Principles. Bunny, a similar tool released by the same developers demonstrates the potential for reduced-scope but production-ready federation, and the alignment of 5STES to the OMOP CDM means that for organisations undertaking OMOP data conversion, they will have fulfilled a critical component of federated analytics that is required for 5STES to work.

There are other, wider, challenges outside of the 5STES tool itself applicable to individual organisations as well as those attempting to federate. We have discussed challenges around common data models and egress processes. However, there are other operational challenges to consider as well, specifically how organisations operationalise supporting federated analytics. Even where tools are more ‘production ready’ (for example, SACRO – see WP3 Final Report), organisations must first understand the tool, install and test installation/usability, define local processes, create manuals and support documents, and provide training to staff and users. All of this takes significant time and resourcing. With many TREs being expected to fully cost recover (that is, operate independently or without full or partial underwriting), the overhead required to introduce new tools and technologies without appropriate accompanying documentation and support means that initiatives may fail, even if they may enable research and innovation broadly. Whilst this challenge is not specific to 5STES, its very early development stage at the time of feasibility means that it is less likely to have broad uptake until such time as these operational barriers are addressed.

For development and uptake of 5STES, it is important to consider the following observations from the PANORAMA partners:

- Complexity kills adoption. Simpler systems (e.g., Bunny) are adopted; complex architectures are not. The multi-container solution proposed within 5STES needs to remain within a smaller number of containers to support uptake of the tool across a federated ecosystem.
- Local infrastructure diversity is a structural barrier. Given the diversity of infrastructure providers, data models and platform maturity, 5STES must provide a solution that is more ‘plug and play’; whilst it is offered open source, TRE operators may wish to purchase software that is easier to install and maintain since most cannot maintain bespoke microservice deployments.
- Testing and reference implementation is essential. Without an end-to-end demonstration, feasibility remains theoretical. Without successful testing templates, organisations will struggle to demonstrate successful usability.
- Accompanying documentation and overarching governance of 5STES is a basic requirement, both for individual organisations and within a federated model.

For some TREs, it is plausible that they could operationalise 5STES at the current development stage where they already have OMOP data available, dedicated platforms, networking and infrastructure support teams, expertise in DevOps. In order to federate, existing Data Sharing Agreements and Data Protection Impact Assessments could be amended with input from technical teams, but may require additional supporting material for IG colleagues to understand federated analytics, and federated workflows must be clearly defined and documented.

7. Conclusion

This project set out to explore the feasibility of implementing the 5STES federated architecture across the PANORAMA partners' (Yorkshire & Humber NHS SDE, North East North Cumbria NHS SDE and North West NHS SDE, and facilitated by researchers from the University of Sheffield) heterogeneous infrastructures, and to assess whether the current 5STES design is likely to be adoptable, maintainable, and beneficial across a wider federated ecosystem. Across both the feasibility assessment and the risk analysis, a clear pattern emerged that, whilst 5STES currently demonstrates promising architectural concepts, it is not at the stage where the necessary requirements exist for PANORAMA partners to deploy into real world environments for testing.

Three types of issues emerged in the feasibility assessment: (1) local constraints that are important but not general blockers; (2) the tool itself is still a prototype stage, which is expected in research software but is not suitable for live environments to support business as usual operations; (3) wider limitations around data structure, egress processes and general factors that may prevent utility in real-world settings. The main challenges at this stage is that the microarchitecture for 5STES is currently too complex, particularly in a federated context, and insufficiently aligned with operational realities of SDEs to support near-term adoption. Governance and documentation are critical for organisations to progress uptake and meet information security and information management requirements. However, challenges identified are not fundamental blockers, but rather issues of architectural direction, missing implementation patterns, or areas where the 5STES team could provide more simplified approaches and appropriate documentation to satisfy information risk assessments.

5STES most certainly *could* be viable for some SDEs in the medium term *if* architectural simplifications, clearer federation patterns, and reduced operational overhead become priorities.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendix A: PANORAMA Partner 1 feasibility report

Overall Findings: 5STES is not able to be put into production and certainly not to be used with any sensitive data in our environment. It will require significant engineering changes from the Platforms team to be brought into use and these installation and maintenance costs would be ongoing as the 5STES system evolves. The current implementation seems to be focussed on the level of a single SDE and there are many open questions as to how the software would be operationalised, how governance would work, and how the cost of operations would be met as the scale increases across the partners. For Partner 1, there is a significant opportunity cost as the efforts to implement 5STES would take away from other business critical tasks at this time.

Feasibility considerations

The end goal of this document is to determine if 5STES could form the basis of a system that a motivated researcher could use to query data across multiple SDEs. Broadly the considerations are as follows;

- Will the changes to our SDS that this will require add unacceptable risks of data disclosure?
- Is the system affordable, both in terms of the initial setup and the ongoing costs?
- Can this be made simple enough for a researcher to be able to use it and reassemble the data?
- Will the data retain its scientific value after conversion to OMOP?
- What will motivate researchers providing data to allow others access?

Architecture considerations

Authentication to either of the layers is handled by Keycloak, and will need to be integrated with the current internal ADFS/EntraID/[NHS CIS2](#). However, some users may not have a login and this would require either adding another SSO provider or managing credentials for an individual.

At Partner 1, each TRE layer will have to be replicated within each project workspace, according to the following diagram:

For our purposes, the submission layer containers may be able to be replaced by AWS Cloud Native equivalents, such as Amazon MQ for Rabbit MQ, RDS for Postgres, S3 for Minio.

SOPs for each of the layers and roles within 5STES must be documented by developers before being able to be translated into local SOPs.

Technical-operational challenges

Some of these risks are only relevant if the system is expanded across multiple TREs, but should the system not cover the majority of TREs the benefits will be reduced. The technical risks to this project centre around the level of maturity of 5STES and its origin as a research project rather than a software product and the effort to make this transition should not be underestimated. The project is in a state of flux and has multiple stakeholders with development shared between them. Examples of this flux include:

- A recent yet-to-be-finished website with significant errors and 404s.
- Replacing the previous task execution service (Hutch) with a Funnel and Trino service.
- A new policy where data access details (such as database hostnames, username and password and schema) are stored in each TRE layer and injected into the submission json before being sent to Funnel, that is undocumented.

Examples of the immaturity of the project:

- No well-defined branching policy to separate future feature development from security fixes.
- No evidence of any software testing; although it does rest on solid components, such as Keycloak, Postgres, Minio, Funnel, and Trino.
- Using insecure policies for passwords, such as [storing passwords in environment variables](#).

- There is no policy on the length of time between a security incident being reported and the release of a change which addresses this.

This last point is especially relevant, as we rebuild our containers every 30 days. If a security issue was detected by CrowdStrike, or if the resultant container was not compatible with CrowdStrike, we would have to disable parts of the service using those containers. This could be a problem with the custom containers provided, such as submission-ui and -api, tre-ui and -api, and egress-ui and -api.

There is also uncertainty as to the resilience of the system as during an upgrade as well as the amount of effort this would require. Would this require a maintenance window, and would this need to be co-ordinated with other TREs? Waiting for an agreed maintenance window could limit our ability to quickly respond to security issues.

It should be noted that there's nothing in the broad architecture which is fundamentally wrong, and the egress mechanism looks similar to the egress mechanism in development by the Platforms team; it just needs significantly more work. Whether there is the will and the resources to address this is an additional risk.

RDS isn't made available through [our current AWS build] and users can't install databases through their EC2 instances.

It is not possible to comment on any technical issues with an orchestrating layer above that of an individual SDE as this currently does not exist.

Governance-operational challenges

There are issues in this project that need to be agreed between all participating SDEs and these don't currently exist. For instance, what is the policy for handling both the authorised and unauthorised escape of Personally Identifiable Information (PII), It is unclear where the responsibility for co-ordinating these actions will lie and how this will be funded over the lifetime of the project. It seems unavoidable that anyone running a query or allowing egress will have to be contractually bound.

It is hard to see how this will function without a central organisation to co-ordinate. For instance a central repository would be needed showing which databases each TRE holds and a researcher responsible for each. The federation may need to run a central clearing house to distribute tasks to each of the SDE's submission layers. These researchers' identities would also need to be validated.

Depending on the setup of the TRE, an execution may cost the researcher money (it will in our instance). How would these costs be managed, particularly if the underlying data is not exactly mapped consistently into a common data model?

Also, each SDE will need to fund a team to assess egress requests, create projects, permit TREs to be added to projects, and allow users to run queries on their TREs. This will either be manually time consuming or require automation, incurring unallocated expense in either case.

Tasks required to put 5STES into production

This should not be taken to be an exhaustive list and may also change as we find better solutions or the 5STES project changes (likely, as it is still very much in development).

1. Where AWS equivalents aren't available, fork the container build code into the DSH repository so that it can be built, scanned by Crowdstrike and pushed to ECR.
2. Build an AWS account for the Submission Layer, needs to be accessible to the entire internet, or at the very least to NHS and TUOS IPs.
3. Create a Transit gateway between each project and the submission layer account. Policies must be put in place to prevent communication between project subnets. Known necessary connections would be from the project subnet's TRE-api to the Submission Bucket.
4. Test for performant compatibility with Crowdstrike container sidecars for containers, applying Crowdstrike to EC2 machines.
5. Incorporate this into Infrastructure as Code (IaC) to automate the creation of the TRE infrastructure in each DSH project subnet.
6. Replacement of all hard-coded secrets with AWS key management system versions.
7. Place user facing code behind a load balancer.
8. Incorporate SACRO into the Egress mechanism. This would mean that there would be changes required to the TRE layer.
9. Any modifications to the Trino layer to handle Parquet, yet retain compatibility with 5STES deployments in other SDEs.
10. Build specific data analysis containers required by users.
11. Set up and maintain OIDC connections.
12. Significant automated testing to check UI, logins, https security which could be run after each update.

Financial outlay

Currently cost for employees divides into setup development time, ongoing maintenance, such as porting our changes into new versions, and support from the SDS team to create projects, approve queries and allow egress. 0.2 FTE for an experienced member of Platforms should be a baseline for the ongoing maintenance.

[Seq](#) requires a licence if used in a production environment.

There will be costs associated with adding all of these systems, especially if RDS is used. These could be mitigated by buying longer contracts for the more expensive systems. Breaking up the code into lambdas would lower costs but would probably be too much of an initial outlay and require significant backporting of new features.

Additional observations

[Bunny](#) is the Federated Analytics solution to simpler problems such as finding out how many patients meet a study's criteria and how these patients are distributed across criteria like age. It is again designed to work with OMOP Common Data Model. Much like the TRE-Layer in 5STES, Bunny exists inside each project in our environment, where it queries the data.

From a quick view of the code, this is what I would like 5STES to look like. A lot of this work has been done by the 5STES team who we've been liaising with, so I hope this methodology and usability consideration gets incorporated into the 5STES project!

Again, as with 5STES, there is a standard problem that data in our DSH won't be in a standard relational database format; the service uses Parquet files with DuckDB. Looking at the repo, this has now been addressed (<https://github.com/Health-Informatics-UoN/hutch->

[bunny/pull/199](#) albeit very recently (15th September). There are operational advantages to this for us; using a relational database means we would have to co-ordinate with a researcher to obtain all the connection parameters and then create AWS secrets for those and restart the containers. If those were to change, we'd repeat the process. This will mean adding DuckDB to Nexus Sonatype after getting Infosec approval.

Appendix B: PANORAMA Partner 2 feasibility report

Overall Findings: 5STES is not able to be put into production and not yet able to be used with any sensitive data in our environment. It will require significant engineering changes from the infrastructure team to integrate with existing systems, security controls and assurance audits.

Although the individual components of the system appear to be well architected, it's not readily apparent how the implementation would operate across multiple SDEs, how activity would be orchestrated between those SDEs, and any consideration of new risks that would be introduced within a multi-SDE environment. The security boundary for the overall solution is also unclear - to what extent is each SDE able to fully secure the solution, and where are they relying on security practices from other SDEs. For example, are inbound queries received from other SDEs considered to be safe, or untrusted, and what guarantees or support do the various components provide to support that.

For Partner 2, there is a significant opportunity cost as the efforts to implement 5STES would take away from other business critical tasks at this time.

Feasibility considerations

The end goal of this document is to determine if 5STES could form the basis of a system that a motivated researcher could use to query data across multiple SDEs. Broadly the considerations are as follows;

- Will the changes to our SDS that this will require add unacceptable risks of data disclosure?
- Is the system affordable, both in terms of the initial setup and the ongoing costs?
- Can this be made simple enough for a researcher to be able to use it and reassemble the data?
- Will the data retain its scientific value after conversion to OMOP?
- What will motivate researchers providing data to allow others access?

Architecture considerations

Authentication to either of the layers is currently handled by Keycloak, whereas authentication for all other components across the SDE, whether for users or applications, are managed via the cloud identity service provider (Azure Entra).

The use of an additional identity manager would result in significant amounts of additional management and governance documentation, particularly given the heightened risks of authenticating federated queries. Operationally, the SDE would look to federate users between keycloak and the main Azure Entra provider to reduce the need to duplicate users (and maintain duplicate user onboarding / management processes etc), but this similarly adds additional complexity to onboarding and is not a process that is currently documented or supported.

A review of the code includes many specific references to keycloak, but without more detailed investigation it's unclear as to the extent that this could be abstracted into a generic authentication provider.

Ideally, some other similar open-source based infrastructure used by 5STES would be able to be replaced with cloud-based managed alternatives. This would provide tighter integration with existing logging, monitoring and assurance tools, alignment with e.g. security updates and patching, and reduce the maintenance overhead for SDE operational teams. These areas would include:

- RabbitMQ. Ideally, support the use of existing cloud based queue services (e.g. Amazon MQ, or Azure Service Bus). Unlike AWS and GCP though, Azure does not have a native RabbitMQ (AMQP 0.9.1) -compatible queue. The use of the EasyNetQ library within the code suggests a tighter coupling to RabbitMQ specifically though.
- Postgres. No specific dependencies on a self-hosted postgres were identified and this appears to be replaceable with a managed postgres database.
- MinIO. Ideally, this would be replaceable with native connectivity to cloud storage accounts (S3, Azure Blob, etc). The recent closure of the open source MinIO project would now limit the use of this service in a production system.
- Seq. This would not be suitable for a production environment without licensing, at which point cloud-native logging providers are likely to be better integrated and more cost effective.

The dedicated parts of the solution - e.g. Bunny, Funnel, etc - would then operate against this managed infrastructure. This minimises the amount of specific maintenance that would be required when operating, and provides significantly higher levels of support across the whole solution.

Implementation would likely need to follow the same per-workspace requirement as Partner 1, where the duplicated infrastructure would create further issues around assurance and monitoring.

Technical-operational challenges

The technical risks to this project centre around the level of maturity of 5STES and its origin as a research project rather than an 'enterprise-ready' software product and the effort to make this transition should not be underestimated. We would share the concerns previously recorded within the equivalent section in Appendix 1.

SDEs operate under strict security and assurance guidance, and with close alignment to the [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments](#) (SATRE) requirements. Federation with other SDEs will require new elements of inbound and outbound connectivity to another SDE where existing SDE boundaries are highly restricted. The combination of the current 5STES maturity in both functionality and process, together with the increased security risks resulting from deployment of any federation solution, means this could not be safely deployed to a production environment in the current state.

This creates a difficult challenge for the 5STES project. The increased functionality required by the 'enterprise ready' solution is not novel, interesting, likely to benefit 5STES as a research project, and would add additional costs and maintenance to the solution. But without that work, SDEs are unlikely to be able to adopt 5STES within a production environment and to be able to use it for other research projects.

As Partner 1 has raised, it is also not clear what technical infrastructure should be in place to support orchestration between SDEs. This will raise additional technical concerns, particularly around consistency and trust. For example:

- Would all SDEs have to operate the same version of 5STES? What degree of backward compatibility may be in place? Where does federation with older versions introduce security risks?
- What processes are in place to trust queries / results from other SDEs? Could queries be signed by the source SDE and verified by the destination SDE? Should queries be entirely untrusted and assumed to be malicious until verified?
- To what extent can or should support be added to monitor and prevent denial of service, differential or jigsaw attacks on the destination SDE? Similarly, can a destination SDE package result in a way which would result in malicious operation against the source SDE?
- If orchestration or user management is centralised, what new attack vectors and threats does that introduce? What assurance can the central service provide to connecting SDEs?

Governance-operational challenges

We would agree with all of the challenges raised by Partner 1 in this area.

Financial outlay

Deployment cost of the current solution would fall into:

- Licence costs. Seq, and MinIO would require commercial licences.
- Governance and assurance. Duplication of identity and security management with components such as Keycloak would require review and adaptation of existing user management processes, onboarding and offboarding, etc. Aspects of processes such as CE+ or ISO27001 would be duplicated. Security assessments, and especially with cross-SDE communication, are likely to be significant. Given the access to production data, and the effective introduction of a new means to ingress/egress that data, a penetration test of the solution would be expected to be required at least by a collaboration of SDEs, if not individually.
- IT Installation. We would expect the initial installation and configuration of the software to be a relatively small aspect of the overall cost. The installation process is well documented and packaged.
- IT support and maintenance. The relatively complex architecture of the overall solution, combined with the relative immaturity of the core software, is likely to result in frequent updates and changes. It is also likely to introduce a number of subtle issues and in case of failure it may be difficult to identify the specific architectural component that has failed. The expected need to remain consistent with security/assurance requirements, and also to keep in step with other SDEs, means this update process needs to be simple and robust with significant support for backward compatibility and data persistence.

Appendix C: PANORAMA Partner 3 feasibility report

This study evaluates the feasibility of deploying the Five Safes Test Execution Service (5STES) within [Partner 3], hosted on Microsoft Azure. 5STES aims to support secure, federated analytics by executing standardised analyses across multiple TREs without moving raw sensitive data. We use Azure-native architecture with an Application Gateway, Web Application Firewall (WAF), and private endpoints for all public DNS, which introduces specific considerations for deploying 5STES.

Summary

5STES provides a promising framework for federated analytics but is not yet production-ready in the Azure environment. A test deployment highlighted several challenges related to:

- Microservice complexity and container orchestration.
- Integration with Azure-native identity systems and private network endpoints.
- OMOP CDM compatibility and Trino connectors for non-relational data.
- Governance, egress, and operational workflows.

The study concludes that we could deploy a simplified or “Bunny-style” 5STES variant for testing and internal validation. Full federated deployment will require additional engineering, identity federation alignment, and standard operating procedures.

Feasibility considerations

The end goal of this document is to determine if 5STES could form the basis of a system that a motivated researcher could use to query data across multiple SDEs. Broadly the considerations are as follows;

- Will the changes to our SDS that this will require add unacceptable risks of data disclosure?
- Is the system affordable, both in terms of the initial setup and the ongoing costs?
- Can this be made simple enough for a researcher to be able to use it and reassemble the data?
- Will the data retain its scientific value after conversion to OMOP?
- What will motivate researchers providing data to allow others access?

Architecture considerations

- Microservice/Container Architecture: 5STES requires 15–25 containers per TRE, secure secret storage, monitoring, and patching. Azure TRE with private endpoints may restrict container-to-container communication. Use of Azure Kubernetes Service (AKS) could simplify orchestration but increase complexity.
- Network & Private Endpoints: Application Gateway with WAF and private DNS endpoints restricts direct public access. TRE-to-TRE communication will require careful

configuration of private peering or VPN tunnels while ensuring encrypted channels. Minimal port configurations and pre-agreed inter-TRE trust models are essential.

- Authentication & Identity Federation: Keycloak in 5STES must integrate with AzureAD/Entra for identity federation. Native support for AzureAD/Entra, including SCIM for automated provisioning and MFA enforcement, is critical. Multi-partner trust agreements and auditability must be defined for federated workflows.
- Data Storage & OMOP CDM Implementation: 5STES relies on Trino to query OMOP-mapped datasets. NWSDE stores data in Azure Data Lake (Parquet/Delta), requiring Hive/Iceberg connectors. OMOP mapping must be synchronised across TREs to support federated analysis.
- Egress: Manual egress approval aligns with Five Safes principles. Integration with SACRO or similar auditing tools is recommended to maintain governance and versioning. Egress processes must align with Azure security policies and network isolation requirements.

Technical-operational challenges

- Container communication may be blocked by private endpoints; careful configuration of VNET peering, Application Gateway rules, and WAF policies is required.
- Keycloak integration with AzureAD/Entra for federation is complex and requires ongoing management.
- Trino connectors for Parquet/Delta may require additional metadata configuration.
- Manual egress processes may create bottlenecks in federated workflows.
- AKS or other orchestration platforms introduce operational overhead for patching, monitoring, and disaster recovery.

Governance-operational challenges

- Standard Operating Procedures for egress, identity management, and inter-TRE workflows must be developed.
- Incident response and audit procedures must accommodate federated workflows and private network constraints.
- Staff training and operational readiness require dedicated resources to manage container orchestration, data mapping, and egress approvals.
- Liability, assurance, and cross-TRE agreements must be formalised for federation.

Tasks required to put 5STES into production

1. Deploy and configure containers on AKS or VM-based container instances with private endpoint connectivity.
2. Integrate Keycloak with AzureAD/Entra for SSO and identity federation.
3. Configure Application Gateway/WAF rules to allow inter-TRE messaging while maintaining private endpoint isolation.

4. Map datasets to OMOP CDM and ensure Trino connectors support Azure Data Lake (Parquet/Delta).
5. Standard operating procedures for egress, auditing, and cross-TRE communication.
6. Conduct automated testing for UI, authentication, network connectivity, and workflow execution.
7. Integrate SACRO or equivalent for audit, provenance, and versioning of federated outputs.
8. Train staff on operational procedures and maintain CI/CD pipeline for container updates.

Financial Outlay

- Initial Setup:
 - Platform engineering for AKS deployment and private endpoint networking.
 - Identity federation integration with AzureAD/Entra.
 - OMOP mapping and Trino connector configuration.
 - Security assessment and WAF rule configuration.
- Ongoing Maintenance:
 - Container orchestration updates and monitoring.
 - Egress approvals and auditing (~0.2 FTE minimum).
 - Security and compliance monitoring.
- Licensing Costs:
 - Seq, MinIO (if used), or Azure-native equivalents.
 - Optional SACRO integration for output auditing.

Additional observations

Deploying 5STES in our Azure TRE is technically feasible but will require substantial engineering effort and governance alignment. Key challenges include integrating with private endpoints, managing container orchestration in AKS, and ensuring identity federation via AzureAD/Entra. A simplified deployment or centrally managed service is recommended for initial testing and gradual scaling across federated TREs.